

REALITIES OF THE TIME: CHRONIC PYELONEPHRITIS AND PREGNANCY

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ABSTRACT

The paper analyzes the literature data on chronic pyelonephritis in pregnant women, on the course and complications of pregnancy against the background of pyelonephritis, the occurrence of comorbidity phenomena, the impact of changes in the cardiovascular system on the course of pregnancy, on the fetus, on childbirth and the postpartum period. The literature was analyzed to identify predictors of comorbidity. Methods for early diagnosis and prevention of complications arising against the background of comorbidity in pregnant women are proposed.

Relevance. The processes occurring in the body of a pregnant woman and their influence, both on the pregnant woman herself and on the fetus, have always been relevant. According to the frequency of occurrence of somatic diseases in pregnant women, one of the most frequent is chronic pyelonephritis. This disease in itself complicates the course of pregnancy and childbirth, as practice shows against the background of pyelonephritis in pregnant women in the second and third trimesters, there are also complications from the cardiovascular system.

The results of the study of Valts I.A. and others (2018) confirmed the adverse effect of cardiovascular pathology on the gestational process: the ability to cause

complications during pregnancy (threatened miscarriage, preeclampsia), childbirth (untimely discharge of amniotic fluid 25.3%, bleeding 13.9%, intrauterine fetal hypoxia 12 %, labor anomalies 17.1%), in the postpartum period (suture failure 6.34%, lactostasis 5.1%), which adversely affect the health of the mother and child [4]. Object. To analyze the data of modern literature to identify and study the phenomena of comorbidity in pregnant women with pyelonephritis. On the basis of the studied data, to determine the predictors contributing to the development of complications of pregnancy and childbirth.

Introduction. L.O. Paendi et al (2012) state that the incidence of women increases from

the prepubertal period, and reaches 82% of accumulated diseases by adolescence. The birth contingent is formed from young women, among whom 42% suffer from anemia, 21% from chronic pyelonephritis, 11% from chronic arterial hypertension, etc. Almost all extragenital diseases preceding pregnancy lead to systemic changes in the hemodynamics of the microcirculation, including the uterus [16]. According to M. L. Chernenkov (2011), in pregnant women living in the Udmurt Republic, urinary tract diseases were diagnosed in 53-54%, according to WHO - 23.6%. Pyelonephritis takes the 2nd place in the structure of extragenital pathology, accounting for 10-12%. With pyelonephritis, every third pregnant woman is diagnosed with: colpitis, cervicitis of both mixed bacterial and bacterial-viral etiology, bacterial vaginosis - in every fourth woman, vaginal dysbiosis with a lactobacilli content of less than 1000 CFU / ml - in 93% [21].

Chronic pyelonephritis continues to be an urgent problem due to its high prevalence, insufficient knowledge of etiopathogenesis, long-term recurrent course, and low treatment efficiency [11, 16]. Kidney diseases have an adverse effect on the course of pregnancy, childbirth, the postpartum period, and the condition of the fetus [16, 20]. Pyelonephritis is the most common clinical form (up to 10-12%) among the pathological processes in the kidneys observed in pregnant women and puerperas. In every third of them, pyelonephritis occurs for the first time during pregnancy or is detected in the postpartum period [11,16].

According to I.V. Latisheva (2006), cardiovascular diseases are the main extragenital pathology of pregnant women;

in recent years, the frequency of these diseases has increased by 1.5-2 times. Conducting a retrospective analysis, the scientist noted that among the main nosological forms, vegetative-vascular dystonia ($6.23 \pm 0.57\%$), prolapse ($3.20 \pm 0.41\%$) and mitral valve insufficiency ($1.99 \pm 0.0\%$) were the most common. (33%), rheumatism ($2.32 \pm 0.35\%$). $1.65 \pm 0.30\%$ of women suffered from neurocirculatory dystonia, $1.10 \pm 0.25\%$ from hypertension, $1.05 \pm 0.24\%$ from cardiosclerosis, $0.50 \pm 0.17\%$ from myocardial dystrophy, combined aortic-mitral defect $0.33 \pm 0.13\%$, myocarditis - $0.22 \pm 0.11\%$, atrial septal defect - $0.17 \pm 0.10\%$. In addition, one case of pulmonary valve insufficiency, tricuspid valve insufficiency, dextrocardia, and jugular vein ectasia was noted. The presence of two or more cardiovascular diseases was registered in 73 ($4.03 \pm 0.46\%$) women in labor [9].

According to Styazhkin S.N. et al. (2015) among extragenital diseases that complicate the course of pregnancy and childbirth, pathology of the kidneys and urinary tract ranks second after heart and vascular diseases. At the outpatient stage of monitoring pregnant women in the antenatal clinic, kidney diseases are observed in 30-35% of pregnant women. Most often, pyelonephritis (10-12%), asymptomatic bacteriuria (6-10%), and much less frequently (0.1-0.2%) glomerulonephritis, urolithiasis, and cystitis are detected [19].

As can be seen from the data of this authors, the occurrence of cardiovascular pathology in pregnant women is associated with the general condition of women. As you know, during pregnancy, the cardiovascular system undergoes changes for the blood supply of two organisms, which in itself is a

load on the circulatory system. This change also applies to the renal system, filtration occurs more and more. Over time, the enlarged pregnant uterus constrains the organs of the abdominal and retroperitoneal cavities, also acting as an additional load. All this leads to changes that lead to complications of pregnancy and further childbirth.

Pregnancy worsens the course of pyelonephritis. Factors contributing to the exacerbation of the chronic focus of infection in the kidneys are hormonal, humoral and anatomical changes in the body of pregnant women. Important in the occurrence of violations of the urodynamics of the upper urinary tract are changes in the anatomical and topographic relationships due to the pregnant uterus [11,12,16].

The leading diseases in the nosological structure of maternal mortality are extragenital diseases. Preeclampsia / eclampsia and obstetric bleeding have lost their leading positions, the main ones in the structure of extragenital diseases are infectious diseases, benign and malignant tumors, diseases of the heart and blood vessels. The increase in the role of extragenital diseases in the structure of maternal mortality is due, among other factors, to an increase in the number of

comorbid conditions and polymorbidity in pregnant women, which can be considered as risk factors for the development of deaths during pregnancy and childbirth [13, 21].

Conclusion. Based on the foregoing, we can say that pyelonephritis and cardiovascular pathology are currently the leading somatic pathologies that aggravate the course of pregnancy and childbirth, even leading to maternal and / or perinatal mortality.

In itself, there is a lot of data about chronic pyelonephritis and pregnancy, as well as pathologies of the cardiovascular system and pregnancy. But their comorbidity, interrelation and overall effect on the maternal organism and the fetus remains little studied.

It can be reliably said that each of these nosological groups of diseases leads to complications of pregnancy, in particular, in the early stages of pregnancy, toxicosis of pregnant women occurs, the threat of termination of pregnancy, over time, symptoms of a sub- and decompensatory state of the body that "works for two" join.

Risk factors for exacerbation of chronic pyelonephritis are frequent colds, hard work, self-treatment of patients. In addition, careful monitoring of patients during the period of seasonal diseases is necessary.

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